

Employees Job Satisfaction in Telecom Industry at Erode District

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ABSTRACT

Employees job satisfaction is derived from the Latin words “Satis” and “facere”, which means “enough and to do” respectively. Job satisfaction survey can give the more valuable information the perceptions and causes. For satisfaction/dissatisfaction among the employees attitude towards job satisfaction may be either positive or negative. This positive thinking can be re-in forced and negative thinking can be rectified. This survey can be treated as the most effective and efficient way, which makes the workers to express their inner and real feelings undoubtedly. For any future course of action/ development, which involves employee’s participation, is considered. The management will get a picture their employee’s acceptance and readiness. This survey also enables to avoid misinterpretations and helps management in solving problems effectively. It is observed that during study some of the employees accepted the proposal survey research.

Keywords: Telecom industry, Employees Job satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Human resource is considered to be the most valuable asset in any organization. It is the sum-total of inherent abilities, acquired knowledge and skills represented by the talents and aptitudes of the employed persons who comprise executives, supervisors and the rank and file employees. It may be noted here that human resource should be utilized to the maximum possible extent, in order to achieve individual and organizational goals. It is thus the employee's performance, which ultimately decides, and attainment of goals. However, the employee performance is to a large extent, influenced by motivation and job satisfaction

Definition

Job satisfaction refers to a person's feeling of satisfaction on the job, which acts as a motivation to work. It is not the self-satisfaction, happiness or self-contentment but the satisfaction on the job.

Hoppock describes job satisfaction as "any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause and person truthfully to say I am satisfied with my job.

Objectives of the Study

The main aim of the study is to analyze and examine level of job satisfaction among the TELECOM INDUSTRY employees and to know the problems faced by the employees of the various categories. The specific objectives are as follows:

- To present a profile of TELECOM INDUSTRY and organizational structure etc.,
- To observe the level of satisfaction among of employees relating to the nature of the job and other factors.
- To identify the extent of job satisfaction in the TELECOM INDUSTRY employees and its impact on the job performance of the employees.
- To evaluate the working environment in TELECOM INDUSTRY.

Scope of the Study

In the survey, an attempt has been made to analyze the job satisfaction of employees of TELECOM INDUSTRY. The study tries to understand the level of satisfaction among the employees of TELECOM INDUSTRY. It further explains the area on which employees are mostly dissatisfied. Job satisfaction of the employees has been analyzed on the basis of the following seventeen job related factors.

Area of study

Erode is a highly progressive district in Tamil Nadu. It is one of the forerunners in the state in terms of agriculture and industrial activities. The district which is endowed with vast natural and physical resources, is making rapid strides in various fronts. There are seven taluks in this district viz., Erode, Perundurai, Bhavani, Kangeyam, Dharapuram, Gobi and Sathyamangalam. There are three revenue divisions viz., Erode, Gobi and Dharapuram. Erode is the administrative head-quarter of this district. There are 539 villages in the district, spread over 20 community development blocks. There are five municipal towns, or township and 61 town panchayats in this district.

Research Methodology

In the preparation of this report, the researcher the data from different sources. The sources of data as follows:

Primary data:

This data is gathered from first hand information sources by the researcher, this data collection from employees, managers, clerks etc., by administering the questionnaire having face to face interaction with employees.

Secondary data:

This will give the theoretical basis required for the report presentation which can be available from various sources such as magazines, office files, inter office manual and web site.

Data Processing and Analyzing

Data, which is gathered by administering questionnaires, was processed in simple manner to determine the level of satisfaction among employees. Every response was assigned some score based on this overall satisfaction level was determined. Data collected is carefully tabulated and analyzed by using satisfaction methods and also various graphs are used.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1 Are you satisfied with the Wages Paid to You?

Yes	No
78	22

(Data in Percentage)

Interpretation: From the tabular and graphical representation of data, 78 percent of the employees are satisfied with the wages paid to them. Only 22 percent of the employees feel that there should be a hike in wages paid to them.

2 Do You Have any Incentives Wage Schemes for Efficient Work on Your Organization?

Yes	No
69	31

(Data in Percentage)

Interpretation

From the tabular and graphical representation of data, 69 percent of the employees feel that there should be an incentive wage scheme for efficient work in the organization.

3 Are You Satisfied with the Present Working Conditions and Environment?

Yes	No
90	10

(Data in Percentage)

Interpretation: From the tabular and graphical representation of data, almost all the employees are satisfied with the present working conditions and environment.

1 Is the Management Helpful and Sympathetic to Your Problems in

Workstation?

To Some extent	To Large extent
70	30

(Data in Percentage)

Interpretation: From the tabular and graphical representation of data, 70% of the employees feel that the management is sympathetic to some extent in their problems faced at workstation.

2 Does the Management Have Good Relation with the Workers?

To Some extent	To Large extent
70	30

(Data in Percentage)

Interpretation: From the tabular and graphical representation of data, 70% of the employees feel that the management has a good relation with the workers and only 20% of them feel that the management should improve their relation with the workers.

3 Does U Feel that Company Policies Need to be Changed?

To some extent	To Large Extent
63	37

(Data in Percentage)

Interpretation: From the tabular and graphical representation of data, 63% of the employees feel that the company policies should be changed and 40% of them feel that the policies of the company are up to their satisfaction.

4 Does the Company Provide any Training to Improve your Performance? If Yes, are you Satisfied with the Training Provided?

To Some extent	To Large extent
87	13

(Data in Percentage)

Interpretation: From the tabular and graphical representation of data, almost all the employees are satisfied with the training provided by the company to improve their performance.

SUGGESTIONS

- More employees feel that the present management should be changed.
- Majority of the employees feel that there should be an incentive wage scheme for efficient work in the organization.
- The management should be more helpful and sympathetic towards the problems faced by the workers at the workstation.

CONCLUSION

Besides several other factors, the economic development of a country depends upon the effective functioning of employees. In order to achieve this superiors and the state should take necessary steps for the satisfaction of employees in their respective jobs.

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